

In the environment, there are polluting substances such as poisons, chemical compounds, toxic gasses, and bacterial toxins that can cause adverse reactions in human beings when entering the body in different ways (ingestion, inhalation, injection, or absorption). Moreover, **foodborne diseases** (FBDs) refer to sicknesses people get from something they eat or drink that cause disability; not only that, they can also cause severe diarrhea, toxic shock syndrome, debilitating infections such as meningitis, and even death, and one of the main reasons is toxins produced by bacteria or other toxic substances in the food. Unfortunately, It has become one of the main problems in public health worldwide because, according to the WHO, each year, **600 million** people around the world, or **1 out of 10**, become ill after consuming contaminated food. Among all these people, **420,000 die**, including **125,000 children** under 5 years of age, due to the vulnerability of this population to develop a diarrheal syndrome; about 43% of FBDs occur in these patients, and the more concerning issue is about 70% of FBDs result from food contaminated with a microorganism.(Hernández-Cortez et al., 2017) We are further going to discuss the reasons and what could be possible **prevention** for stopping food poisoning that is **caused** by bacteria.

There are two types of bacterial toxin: endotoxin and exotoxin. **Endotoxin** is found only in the cell wall of gram-negative bacteria, specifically in the lipid A portion, while **Exotoxin** is found in both Gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria, which are composed of A and B subunits. Moreover, for Gram-positive pathogens, the most relevant toxins are emetic toxins and diarrheal enterotoxins, which are considered the most important virulence factors of respective foodborne pathogens and a primary cause of related foodborne diseases.

This type of contamination can occur from the crop, in the case of vegetables, or just before eating them due to the consumer's manipulation. These contaminants are carried out in different stages such as agricultural, livestock, and fish production; industrialization (in the case of processed food); marketing (points of sale); and transportation to the final consumer (homes, community dining rooms, and restaurants). (Hernández-Cortez et al., 2017)

Many kinds of microorganisms have been alleged to cause food poisoning merely because they have been found in large numbers in implicated foods, or in the vomits or

stools of patients another interesting part is among those bacteria some of them are natural inhabitants of the intestinal tract of healthy persons and there is no reason other than the circumstantial evidence. In many cases, bacterial toxins can be produced after cooking the food when the temperature is permissible for bacterial growth.

Staphylococcus enterotoxin, ***Salmonella***, and ***Clostridium*** can be used as an example. In the case of *Staphylococcus*, food poisoning can happen after **5-6** hours of consumption if it is handled by someone who already contracted the bacteria. For determining the cause of food poisoning, it's essential to study the food source and patients' samples carefully and we have to be more conscious while consuming the food in these cases epidemiological studies can help trace the outbreak to a specific food item, but testing is complicated by factors like refrigeration and previous bacterial exposure. (Dack, 1947).

Proper cooking and processing of food is crucial as it can prevent most of the foodborne illnesses that can kill bacteria. For that we need to take key measures such as improving personal hygiene, adequate refrigeration, adequate cooking or heat processing of food at a higher temperature, and preventing the holding of food in the melt device at bacterial growth temperatures and three methods must be followed which are education to the people who are preparing the food materials at home and other food handlers so that they have to take proper personal measures; then prohibiting individuals with absences; and lastly placing food in a cold place at **4°** centigrade or lower of all food to prevent bacterial multiplication and the formation of toxins. For further precaution canned food is always cooked at a higher temperature like **121°C** or higher so that all bacterial spores get destroyed, vegetables from home-canned should be boiled for at least **3-4** minutes before serving cooked meat at **74°C** temperature to avoid bacterial contamination, all the containers, and equipment that previously had contact with raw meat/eggs should wash and sanitation. In the time of handling raw or uncooked foods then wash hands and use disposable plastic gloves before chilling separate meat and other food stock because cross-contamination of undercooked or raw foods is the main cause of infection due to contamination or raw produce being in contact with cooked materials. By using Hazard Analysis of Critical Control Points

bacteria should be removed from the meat by cleaning, grasping, and freezing of meats. (Guptaa, & Chaudharyb, 2022)

In the end, we understand that bacterial toxins pose significant public health risks. For that reason, proper food handling, thorough cooking, and safe storage methods are essential for preventing foodborne illnesses. Public education on personal hygiene and food safety practices is crucial, as is maintaining food at appropriate temperatures to inhibit bacterial growth because of the implementation of measures such as Hazard Analysis of Critical Control Points (HACCP) and proper food processing, including high-temperature cooking and sanitation, can effectively minimize the risk of food contamination and related health complications.